

Inaugural International Forum on World Universities
Davos, Switzerland
January 31st – February 2nd, 2008

**University Role in Promoting Leadership and Commitment to the
Community**

Osama A. Marzouk
Department of Engineering Science and Mechanics, MC 0219
Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University
Blacksburg, VA 24061, USA

Abstract	1
Keywords	2
Introduction.....	2
Virginia Tech – a model land-grant university	3
Leadership Seminar Series – improving leadership skills	3
Description.....	3
Sample Topics.....	4
Observations	4
World Simulation Game-Workshop	5
Description.....	5
The Workshop.....	5
Comments	5
VT ENGAGE – early scholarly engagement.....	6
Description.....	6
Kickoff Event.....	6
Progress.....	7
Annual University-Community Partnership Conference.....	7
Description.....	7
Scope and Concerns	7
Some Topics.....	8
Engagement Projects and Students	8
Concluding Remarks.....	9
Some References.....	9

Abstract

Leadership can be defined as caring about people and working toward completing a mission. Consequently, there is a strong relationship between leadership and community service (or engagement with the community). Part of the mission of the university or college should be to develop the students' leadership skills and their feeling of commitment toward their community (at a small and local level) and society (at a large level). I present some programs that were established for this purpose, and discuss the reaction of the students to them and how these programs were successful in achieving

their goals and how they helped the students define and understand leadership and participate actively in service projects for the welfare of the community.

Keywords

University, Leadership, Community, Engagement

Introduction

For years and years, universities have been conceived as academic institutions whose role is confined in teaching disciplines of knowledge subjects and granting relevant degrees. It is true that there are, fortunately, many cases where this is not exactly true, and we see strong collaboration in these cases between the university and the organizations and communities of the society, where the academic knowledge and scholarship extend beyond the bounds of the campus and reach members of the society directly or indirectly. As we enter a new century, many universities revisited and amended their missions, and incorporated internal changes to strengthen the connection between their educational programs and the society needs, especially by establishing new programs or modifying existing ones. As an indication of the increasing emphasis on this role of the university, the Carnegie Foundation (an organization that classifies higher education institutions in the United States) has introduced in December 2006 a new classification based on community engagement. There are two topics that have benefitted from this trend, which are leadership and community service. Proper attention to these components of the educational process is important in order to develop sufficient leadership skills among students and to raise the level of responsibility they feel toward the local and global communities. This does not only impact the students, who will gain helpful skills and feel more involved in the society; it also enhances the public image of the university and directly affects the society, which will benefit more from the students during and after their college study.

There are two related issues that should be examined carefully in order to develop effective programs targeting leadership and community service. The first is the perception of these topics by college students, especially at the early stage of college study. The second is what the university should provide to the students in order to promote these topics. I will address these issues here while describing and commenting on some of the ongoing programs that have been established at Virginia Tech, one of the leading universities in the United States, that promote leadership and engagement on campus. Participation in most of these programs is open to both undergraduate and graduate students; some of them are open to faculty and staff members as well. They include seminars, discussion groups, interactive sessions, large-scale engagement projects, workshops, simulation games, and conferences. I consider here four programs, two of which focus on leadership, whereas the other two focus on service and engagement.

Virginia Tech – a model land-grant university

The word “land-grant university” refers to a type of higher education institutions in the United States that had originally received federal benefits in terms of state lands, and had a mission to teach agriculture, military tactics, and the mechanic arts as well as classical studies so that the working classes, who de facto did not have access to higher education, could obtain a liberal, practical education. This type of universities was established through the first Morrill Act (1862). Subsequent legislations have been made to include financial federal support to these universities on annual basis. Currently, there is at least one land-grant institution in each of the fifty states of the United States. So, being a land-grant university implies certain level of dedication to the development and outreach to the society. As a result, it is not surprising to see these universities paying special attention to service and engagement programs on their campuses so that students learn the importance of employing the knowledge and skills they gain through their studies in serving and cooperating with members and organizations of the local and global communities. In the state of Virginia, there are two land-grant universities. Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University (known as Virginia Tech, VTech, and VT) is one of them. It is also a leading research university at the national level. It has about 30,000 students, at both the undergraduate and graduate levels. Virginia Tech is a model university that has taken long and successful steps toward designing, teaching, and implementing engagement and leadership programs for its students. The university motto since 1896 is “Ut Prosim”, which is the Latin translation of “That I May Serve”. For this reason, I chose Virginia Tech and some of its programs to be presented here and I will describe and comment on these programs and their achievements. In addition, my affiliation with Virginia Tech and my four-year experience there as a graduate student, an instructor, and a leader officer in more than one student organization, enabled me to thoroughly examine and participate in the various programs that are considered here, and to observe the reaction of the participants and evaluate the achievement of these programs.

Leadership Seminar Series – improving leadership skills

Description

The leadership seminar series (LSS) program is sponsored by the Leadership Development Office, Department of Student Activities. It is open to the university community (undergraduate and graduate students, and faculty and staff members). However, after two years of observation, I found that most of the participants are first- and second-year undergraduate students. To encourage participation, the program provides a certificate that attests the participation of the student if he or she attends seven or more seminars (the number was reduced from nine to seven). These certificates are presented at a special event (University Student Leadership Awards) near the end of the academic year. The LSS program provides about eleven seminars and workshops over the entire academic year. They address different aspects of leadership, which are not the same every year. The seminars have different formats, such as lectures, interactive activities, discussion groups, panels, and educational movies. Most seminars include a guest speaker (or a group of speakers). Each seminar lasts for one hour in the evening

(5:30 pm to 6:30 pm), which is convenient to the students since there are fewer classes at that time than in the morning or the afternoon.

Sample Topics

To give the reader a better view about the LSS program, I list some of the topics that have been covered recently or have been scheduled to be covered in the near future.

- Diversity 101: My Contributions to a Multicultural Society
- Time Management
- Real World Leadership
- Service Learning
- Leadership for Women
- Spirituality & Leadership
- International Perspective
- Leadership: What Does it Mean to You?
- Finding Your Place Through Student Organizations
- Getting Involved in Your Community
- Is Leadership Really Leadership without Ethics?
- You Can Lead, But Can you Mentor?
- Followership, the Other Side of Leadership
- Gender and Leadership: the Glass Ceiling Revisited
- Making Your Leadership Experience Work for You
- Leadership in a Global Society

We can see that the focus of this program is not limited to ‘pure’ leadership. It acknowledges what I mentioned earlier that leadership has a big connection with service and engagement with the community.

Observations

After more than two years of attending and actively participating in the seminars of this program and observing the students reactions and comments, it became clear that new college students are in need of such seminars that help them define leadership and understand its implications and the characteristics of a successful leader. The students gained a good amount of knowledge and skills related to leadership; such as time management, the difference between local and global leadership, and the difference between mentorship and leadership. Near the end of the program, the participants became more confident in defining leadership and distinguishing it from mentorship or supervising. They also became aware of several required qualities of the leader; which they overlooked at the beginning of the program; such as integrity, decisiveness, and having good personal relationships with the followers.

Most of the students who attended the program at the beginning continued to attend till the end, which reflects how interesting and beneficial this program was for them. However, this number was very small compared to the total number of students (graduate and undergraduate) at the university. I can interpret this as a result of insufficient publicity for the program. The website of the program is not easily reached from the main webpage of the university, and there are very little flyers about the program posted on campus.

The fact that young undergraduate students dominate the attendance of this program reflects little interest in the subject among the older undergraduate students and the graduate ones. This should be taken into consideration by the organizers of such leadership programs. They should introduce new programs or modify the existing ones such that they appeal more to this range of students by offering topics related to leadership in the workplace and teamwork leadership, for example, which are of special interest to those students.

World Simulation Game-Workshop

Description

This is another program that focuses on leadership. Unlike the leadership seminar series program, the world simulation game-workshop is a one-time event rather than a series of events. Also, this program attempts to develop leadership skills at the global or international level. The program is sponsored by the Cranwell International Center (which is the central university unit that coordinates events and programs for international, or non-American, students and provides several immigration services to them as well) and the Council of International Student Organizations. This annual event lasts for three hours in the evening. Again, this is a preferred time to minimize conflicts with classes. The program is open to undergraduate and graduate students.

The Workshop

Since the number of participants in the 2007 program, which took place in November, was limited to 150, interested students had to register online before attending the event. The theme of the event was “How would you run the world?”

Some of the participants formed teams that represent countries. Other participants represented global companies that provide services, such as education, energy, and water. Each team initially had a certain amount of wealth and natural resources in form of a number of tokens. In order to get a service from a company, the team needs to purchase it. Also, they may sell some of their natural resources to companies that use them. The teams can bargain with the companies for better rates. They need to decide the appropriate amounts of services they need in order to develop their country in the best way. Political, economic and military international dilemmas were included in the simulation and the teams needed to deal with them carefully.

Comments

I observed that the majority of the participants were international students and almost no American students attended. Although this can partially be ascribed to the fact that the program announcements indicated that it is organized by the international center and the council of international student organizations, this can also reflect low-level of interest in global leadership among citizen students. Hence, it calls for more attention regarding this part and for raising the awareness about international issues. With today’s globalization, it becomes more important for a successful leader to be aware of what happens outside the ‘geographical or virtual’ borders of his or her organization, community, or nation;

since such external and remote events and their influence can cross these borders directly or indirectly.

The event was very successful not only in developing global leadership skills, but also in raising the awareness among the participating students about international problems that need collective effort and collaboration among the nations in order to overcome, such as global warming, energy resources, and the environment. At the end, each participant was given a T-shirt with a printed design about the workshop (this was a surprise and was not announced prior to the event).

VT ENGAGE – early scholarly engagement

Description

The VT-ENGAGE is a very recent program (started in October 2007), that is coordinated by a special steering committee that includes faculty, staff, students (undergraduate and graduate), administrators, and community leaders. The program requests that each member of the university community, as well as the alumni, pledges ten hours of service work to any of the many organizations and projects that are located locally or remotely. The program has declared a goal of 600,000 service hours (300,000 by the university members and another 300,000 by the alumni) to be performed by the end of the 2007/08 academic year (in May 2008). It is interesting that the program is open to the family members and friends of the university members as well.

Kickoff Event

The university (Virginia Tech) has created a permanent website for this program, which explains the program, its goals, and its recent news. It allows anyone to pledge service hours and update the status of the performed hours as well. However, the university relied on other means to assure that this program is well-announced and publicized on its campus. For this purpose, a kickoff event was arranged on Tuesday, 16 October 2007, and a special flyer was designed and posted in the academic and nonacademic units. The kickoff event lasted for three hours (4 pm – 7 pm) and took place in the central field of the campus. Many service organizations had booths which illustrated how prospective volunteers can participate in these organizations and what kinds of projects are conducted by them. Additional pledging booths were distributed in the field, where volunteers could pledge their service hours (minimum of ten hours per a volunteer) after they decided which organization or project they are interested in. The pledging included filling a small form with information about the volunteer, the service organization or project, and the number of pledged hours. The volunteer signs the form, and receives an attractive gift pen, which bears the word “VT-ENGAGE” and also can produce light. Live and recorded music, free carnival food, and free games helped make the event attractive and successful. It was very nice to see faculty members and university leaders participating with students in this event in a very informal and friendly atmosphere. The kickoff event started with a speech by the Vice Provost for Outreach and International Affairs to introduce this new program.

Progress

- As of 1 November 2007, about 80,000 hours were pledged by the university members.
- On 1 December 2007, this number reached 131,467 hours.
- On 6 January 2008, the number increased to 152,304 hours.

Annual University-Community Partnership Conference

Description

This is another effort made by Virginia Tech to strengthen scholarly engagement and collaboration between the universities, in general, and their communities. This annual conference takes place in the summer (June or July). It is sponsored by multiple units at Virginia Tech, such as the Service-Learning Center, the Community-Campus Partnerships for Health, the Graduate School, and the Office of Multicultural Affairs. The conference is also co-sponsored by the University of Virginia (one of the well-known and ranked universities in the state of Virginia, which is considered to be a peer university of Virginia Tech). While the VT-ENGAGE program addressed engagement and service while reaching a very broad spectrum of participants, the university-community partnership conference is more concerned about the university leaders and the coordinators of service programs. However, graduate students had a role in it (besides attending the sessions and the poster exhibit), where they had a special forum in 2007 about how community calls them back to the university so that they can improve their impact on the community. In addition, the conference attracts faculty members, local government staff, and nonprofit and nongovernmental leaders.

Unlike all other programs mentioned here, this conference has a registration fee, which was US\$ 249 for the two-day 2007 conference (approximately equivalent to 169 Euros or 285 Australian dollars, based on exchange rates of January 2008). Participants from all over the United States attend the conference; they represent universities, colleges, governmental agencies, service centers, and leadership institutes.

Scope and Concerns

In 2006, the third university-community partnership conference addressed the importance of engagement as an inseparable part of the higher education mission. As a follow up in the fourth conference, which was in July 2007, the main theme in 2007 was “How do communities define engagement with institutions of higher education?” The conference explored the perspective of community partners about the collaboration between the university and the community, the implications for communities when they choose engagement with higher education institutions, and the consequences of the situation when communities call forth their universities.

The conference included practical and interactive workshops, case studies, best practice presentations, and a community partners resource fair. It aimed at providing those who participated in the conference with the necessary tools to start their own partnership experience successfully, after being aware of the pitfalls and peculiar issues that are commonly found during partnership development and maintenance.

Some Topics

To give a better idea about the 2007 conference and its objectives, a partial list of the titles of its presentations, sessions, forums, and posters is given below

- How Our Work in Communities Called Us Back to the University: A Graduate Student Forum
- Achieving Authentic Community-Higher Education Partnerships By Mobilizing a National Network of Experienced Community Partners
- Citizen-Driven Planning and Opportunities for Building a Unique Learning Community of Neighborhood Leaders, Students, and Faculty
- Community Initiated Projects: Successes and Challenges
- Community-Campus Partnership for Health National Network
- Social and Economic Change Through Campus-Community Partnership
- The Young Women Leaders Program: Mentoring and Leadership for College Women and Adolescent Girls
- Listening & Learning from Community Voices
- Reciprocity: Community Agencies and Higher Education in Service-Learning
- Building University-Community Partnership to Support Local Economic and Workforce Development
- Developing Partnership for Environmental Service-Learning

Engagement Projects and Students

The keynote speaker session was followed by a facilitated discussion through Story Circles (the technique was introduced by Donna Porterfield from Roadside Theatre in Virginia, USA), which allowed each team (or discussion circle) to share stories about engagement and service projects, and to reflect on the meaning of true engagement. This part of the conference lasted for two hours and half in the afternoon.

I served as a facilitator of one of these circles, which included faculty and staff members from Virginia Tech and the University of Virginia. Fortunately, most the members of this circle had participated or were participating formally (as part of their job responsibilities) or informally in coordinating and supervising one or more service projects at the level of the university, where students (and sometimes the faculty and staff as well) get the chance to volunteer by giving time, effort, or unneeded personal items to members or organizations in the community around the university. What was common in these stories is the strong willingness of the students to participate in these projects, and their high level of dedication to them. In fact, we had an agreement that students who choose to participate in these programs enjoy such work, although it can be arduous and time consuming, and do this repeatedly. One of the outcomes of this story circle is the importance of establishing structured channels for students through which they can give to the community in various ways. It is the responsibility of the university to arrange such channels, in cooperation with existing service organizations on campus, in order to maximize the benefit that community can get from the students.

Concluding Remarks

The educational role of the university, which has been confined for decades in teaching scientific and liberal-arts courses through classical curricula, is evolving in response to the changes and challenges in the twenty first century. The society needs college graduates who are not only equipped with disciplinary and even interdisciplinary knowledge, but also with sufficient leadership skills and engagement experience. This study visited some of the new and old leadership and engagement programs at one of the leading land-grant universities in the United States, Virginia Tech, as a model for other universities and colleges elsewhere. These programs aim at increasing the level of leadership and commitment to the society within the students, and even within the entire university community. However, they attempt to reach this goal from different perspectives and using different approaches.

As a participant and observer, I described two leadership-focused programs and two engagement-focused programs, and commented on their achievements and on the necessary extensions to address some gaps in the students understanding of leadership and in how their effort to give to and serve the community are organized.

It is the responsibility of the university to arrange academic programs that clarify the meaning of leadership, its implications, and its connection to other issues, such as ethics and good leader-followers relationships. These programs might not appeal to the entire spectrum of students (undergraduate and graduate). So, several programs might be needed with different scopes that fit each group individually. Also, publicity of these programs is important and has direct impact on the attendance and participation levels.

Since large-scale leadership requires proper awareness of international issues, it is very useful to include this aspect in any leadership-development programs to ensure proper understanding of the remote events that can eventually influence the local community and one's society.

It is also the responsibility of the university, in cooperation with existing on campus service organizations, to arrange service and community-engagement projects that act as channels that allow students to volunteer their time, effort, or unneeded personal items conveniently and efficiently to the members or organizations in the community who are in need of them.

Some References

The Carnegie Foundation for the Advancement of Teaching
<http://www.carnegiefoundation.org>

About the Land-Grant System
<http://www.wvu.edu/~exten/about/land.htm>

Land Grant Institutions (listed)
http://www.higher-ed.org/resources/land_grant_colleges.htm

Leadership Seminar Series at Virginia Tech
<http://www.uusa.vt.edu/studentActivities/leadershipseminars.php>

The Cranwell International Center (Virginia Tech)
<http://www.uusa.vt.edu/cranwell/>

The Council of International Student Organizations (Virginia Tech)
<http://www.ciso.org.vt.edu/>

VT-ENGAGE (Virginia Tech)
<http://www.engage.vt.edu/>

The Fourth Annual University-Community Partnership Conference: The Community
Calls Forth the University
<http://www.cpe.vt.edu/unicom/>